

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PRIMARY OUTPATIENT MEDICAL CARE IN BULGARIA AND THE USA

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ABSTRACT

Inequalities in the access to and the use of healthcare services at the primary care level are an issue, which challenges researchers to. The results of a questionnaire-styles survey are presented in this article. The survey was conducted in the March 2013 - May 2023 period, using the Google Forms online platform. 395 adult Bulgarian citizens and 387 adult citizens of the US. The results indicate that the access to the GP's office in Bulgaria has become easier for more than half of the respondents (54,18%) due to the reduced number of patients seen in the office during the period analysed. For more than half of the US patients surveyed (53.49%), no change in the access to the OPD was observed, and according to 1/3 of the respondents (29.97%), access has become more difficult due to longer waiting times. The primary mode of contacting a GP in Bulgaria is by telephone (45.82%), while in the USA it is an digital healthcare website (60.47%).

Keywords: primary outpatient care, access, modes of communication, limitations, inequalities.

In both Bulgaria and the USA, a patients' first contact with the healthcare system is comprised of a meeting with their general practitioner. In the context of COVID-19, various restrictions were imposed, which also led to a change in access to primary and specialist outpatient care.

The goal of this survey is to present the views of respondents on their access to outpatient primary care in a pandemic setting.

To realise this goal the following tasks were assigned:

1. Analysing the access to the GP's office during the conditions of Covid-19 and the reasons for change in Bulgaria and the USA.
2. Analysing the patients' contact with their general practitioners by phone in the context of Covid-19 in Bulgaria and the USA.
3. Analysing the modes of contacting the general practitioner in the context of Covid-19 in Bulgaria and the USA.

The study is part of a wider research analysing the health inequalities in Bulgaria and the USA. A survey was distributed in the March 2023 May 2023 period via the Google Forms online platform among 395 adult Bulgarian citizen and SPSS 17.0 was used for processing the results 387 adult US citizens.

An analysis of the sample by gender, showed that the highest proportion of respondents in Bulgaria were women ($n=231$; 58.48%) as opposed to men ($n=164$; 41.52%). In the US, the largest proportion of respondents was also made up of women ($n=229$; 59.17%), while males made up 40.83% ($n=158$).

In terms of social status, in both Bulgaria and the USA, the largest relative share of respondents was made up by workers at 65.06% and 89.15%, respectively.

In order to study and analyse the organization and access to outpatient medical care in the context of COVID-19, in this survey conducted during the March2023 - May2023 period, we sought the patents' opinions on the outpatient care organization during a one-year period

The results to the question "Has your access to the GP /office/changed in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic and in what direction?", showed that that over half of the Bulgarian respondents ($n=214$; 54.18%) experienced access becoming easier due to the reduced number of patients seen in the office (Fig. 1). In 20.51% of respondents, access had become more difficult due to a longer wait outside the doctor's office, and for 19.49% experienced no change.

Figure 1. Has your access to GP (office) changed in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic and in what direction? (in Bulgaria)

The responses to the same question in the USA indicated that over half the respondents $n=207$; 53,49 %) experienced no changes in access (Fig= 2). Nearly 1/3 of respondents ($n=116$; 29,97 %) accounted that access

had become harder due to the longer waiting times for obtaining an appointment at the doctor's office, while 8,53% reported that their access had become harder due to longer waiting times in front of the office.

Figure 2. Has your access to GP (office) changed in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic and in what direction? (in the USA)

Patients' relationship with their general practitioners by telephone in the context of Covid-19 is another focus of our study (Table 1). In Bulgaria, 46.58% ($n=184$) of respondents received a consultation by phone or a returned call from their GP during working hours, and 26.08% ($n=103$) received a telephone consultation or returned call from their GP at any time. This

demonstrates the commitment and empathy of GPs towards the problems experienced by their patients. A little over 1/4 ($n=108$; 27.34%) of patients had a vastly different experience - **they had not received** a phone consultation when calling their GP and were not contacted by the physician at a later point. The reasons for this may be varied - physicians with larger practices ex-

periencing a heavier workload, or them having no interest in the patient's problems, or the patients abusing phone consultations by calling their general practitioner for non-urgent problems. Experience shows that, despite the availability of 24-hour medical "centres", the

majority of patients would rather trust their general practitioner, sometimes resulting in unwarranted calls to the physician at inappropriate times of day.

Table 1.

Changes in patients' contact with their GPS by phone (consultation) in the Covid-19 context in Bulgaria and the USA

RESPONSES	Bulgaria		USA	
	number	%	number	%
I always receive a phone consultation when I call in the GP's working hours and/or a return call from the physician	76	19.24%	56	14.47%
I always receive a phone consultation when I call at any time of the day and/or a return call from the physician	43	10.89%	18	4.65%
I sometimes receive a phone consultation when I call in the GP's working hours and/or a return call from the physician	108	27.34%	81	20.93%
I sometimes receive a phone consultation when I call at any time of the day and/or a return call from the physician	60	15.19%	46	11.89%
I never receive a phone consultation when I call my GP and/or a return call from the physician	108	27.34%	186	48.06%

In the USA, 14,47 % (n=56) of respondents received a consultation by phone or a returned call from their GP during working hours, and 4,65 % (n=18) received a telephone consultation or returned call from their GP at any time. Nearly half (n=186; 48,06 %) of respondents had a vastly different experience - **they had not received** a phone consultation when calling their GP and were not contacted by the physician at a later point. The reasons for this may be varied - physicians with larger practices experiencing a heavier workload, or them having no interest in the patient's problems, or the patients abusing phone consultations by calling their general practitioner for non-urgent problems.

We asked the patients whether they had used any other way to contact their GP in the context of Covid - 19 (Fig. 3). In Bulgaria, phone consultations are the most common way of contacting the general practitioner (n=181; 45,82%), with modern modes of communication like the Viber (n=119; 30,13%) and Messenger (n=61; 15,44%) instant messaging applications and email (n=21; 5,32%) having a not insubstantial share of responses. This exemplifies that GPs have a great workload where it comes to communicating with patients.

Figure 3. Mode of contacting the general practitioner in the context of Covid-19

In the US, when asked if they used any other way to contact their GP in the context of Covid -19 (Fig. 4), the majority of respondents indicated an healthcare website ($n=234$; 60,47 %), while 17.83% ($n=69$) used e-mail to contact their GP and 10.08% ($n=39$) used text

messaging. This exemplifies that GPs have a great workload where it comes to communicating with patients.

Figure 4. Mode of contacting the general practitioner in the context of Covid-19 in Bulgaria

Based on the results presented herein we can draw the following conclusions:

1. Access to the GP's office in Bulgaria has become easier for more than half of the respondents (54,18%) due to the reduced number of patients seen in the office during the period analysed.
2. For more than half of the US patients surveyed (53.49%), no change in the access to the OPD was observed, and according to 1/3 of the respondents (29.97%), access has become more difficult due to longer waiting times.
3. 27.34% of Bulgarians or 48.06% of US patients did not receive consultations by phone by their GP or a return call by the physicians.
4. The primary mode of contacting a GP in Bulgaria is by telephone (45.82%), while in the USA it is an healthcare website (60.47%).

The organisation and access to outpatient care, as one of the elements determining the quality of the health services provided, should be studied and analysed even more thoroughly and comprehensively in the context of a pandemic. Having unhindered access to a GP is a crucial condition for patient satisfaction with outpatient care. This makes it imperative, especially in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic, that outpatient physicians and patients make full use of information and communication technologies and online consultations.

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